

2 Volt Pulse-Driven Josephson Arbitrary Waveform Synthesizer

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Abstract — We created a Josephson Arbitrary Waveform Synthesizer (JAWS) with a root-mean-square (rms) output magnitude of 2 V. This system is composed of two 1 V chips operating on a cryocooler. By controlling the relative phase of the two chips' output voltage, we add the voltages in quadrature and create rms output voltages between (1+1) V=2 V and (1-1) V=0 V. We use this control to compare the two halves of the system as a function of the relative phase, and measure a difference of 8 parts in 10^8 at a nominal rms amplitude of 1 V and 1 kHz.

Index Terms — Digital-analog conversion, Josephson junction arrays, Measurement standards, Signal synthesis, Superconducting integrated circuits, Voltage measurement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The pulse-driven Josephson Arbitrary Waveform Synthesizer (JAWS), also known as the AC Josephson Voltage Standard (ACJVS), was invented in 1995 [1]. In the ensuing years, an important goal has been to increase the rms output of the quantum-accurate waveforms synthesized by this Josephson junction (JJ) based digital-to-analog converter. Audio-frequency voltage calibrations that are performed with thermal voltage converters and impedance measurements, along with other precision measurements, would benefit from rms output voltages above 2 V. The most sensitive range of the converters extends up to 10 V, and a larger output voltage would increase the signal-to-noise ratio of other measurements. JAWS systems with a rms output voltage of 1 V have been demonstrated in the past two years [2]-[4].

We recently implemented a new 2 V JAWS system that combines two 1 V chips on a cryocooler and has an operating current range greater than 1 mA [5]. The two chips are connected in series at cryogenic temperatures using a short copper wire. Each chip is driven by a separate custom, large-memory pulse generator [6]. Further details of the design and operation of this 2 V JAWS system are described in [5].

In this paper, we report for the first time preliminary results of a comparison between two halves of the 2 V JAWS system. Since the two chips are driven with pulses from two separate generators, we can choose to generate waveforms with arbitrary phases (and magnitudes). In particular, this allows us to perform a precision null measurement by generating waveforms that have precisely identical rms magnitudes of 1 V, but are exactly 180° out of phase.

II. JAWS COMPARISON

In Fig. 1 we show the digitized output of the JAWS system generating a 1 kHz waveform with a rms magnitude of 2.0000 V. With this large output voltage, we observe

Fig. 1. Digitally sampled spectral measurements showing a low distortion JAWS output voltage with an rms magnitude of (1+1) V = 2 V (blue), and background noise floor without any JAWS pulses (red). The digitizer was set to its 10 V range with a 1 M Ω input impedance and a sampling rate of 10^6 samples/s. We plot the phase-coherent average of 4 data sets, each taken with a 2 Hz resolution bandwidth.

harmonics that are -123 dBc (decibels below the carrier/fundamental frequency), which are due to nonlinearities in the digitizer [2].

To generate this calculable voltage from the two chips, we must first synchronize the two pulse generators. We start by loading both pulse generators with the same pulse pattern and then tuning the relative delay between the generators. We have arbitrary control over the delay with a fine time step of 70 ps, which is equal to the width of a single pulse. This phase control is displayed in Fig. 2, where we sweep the relative phase between the two generators over 360° and measure the quadrature sum of the 1 kHz waveforms generated by the two chips. Achieving a precision null requires removing a time delay of 111 ns, which is the result of delays in the trigger system and other asymmetries in the two driving circuits. We synchronize the two generators by compensating for this time delay.

We also use the depth of the precision cancellation to place a limit on the difference in the output voltages of the two 1 V chips (similar to [7]) due to any systematic errors. In Fig. 3 we plot the spectrum of the cancelled waveform, that is, the precision null. Each chip is generating a voltage at 1 kHz with an rms magnitude of 1 V, but with a 180° relative phase shift

(to within 70 ps). The precision null has a residual voltage at the fundamental frequency with an rms magnitude of 82 nV. We also observe a harmonic of the fundamental that is -165 dBc (relative to an assumed in-phase carrier with an rms magnitude of 2 V).

Possible explanations for the residual voltage are as follows: (1) differences in pulse arrival time at and within each array; (2) insufficient fine tuning of the relative phase shift between the arrays; and (3) systematic-error voltage signals related to compensation currents driving each JJ array. The small magnitude of the error voltage and the short 70 ps pulse width influence the likelihood of some of these explanations relative to others. This error is interesting and shows the importance of investigating the systematic errors through flat spot measurements for all bias parameters and their phase delays.

III. CONCLUSION

We evaluated the relative performance of the two chips that make up our new 2 V ACJVS system [5]. We observed that the relative error between the two halves of the system is of the order of 8 parts in 10^8 , with each half generating a 1 kHz waveform with an output rms magnitude of 1 V. In the future, we intend to extend this comparison to other frequencies and present an analysis of systematic errors.

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Fig. 2. Measured complex rms magnitude of fundamental tone at 1 kHz with a relative phase shift of 2° between data points, and theoretical expectation (line, no fit parameters).

Fig. 3. Digitally sampled spectral measurement showing a low distortion JAWS output voltage with an rms magnitude of $(1-1) \text{ V} = 0 \text{ V}$ with 82 nV remnant (blue), and background noise floor without any JAWS pulses (red). The digitizer was set to its 2 V range with a 1 M Ω input impedance and a sampling rate of 10^6 samples/s. We plot the phase-coherent average of 16 data sets, each taken with a 2 Hz resolution bandwidth.

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